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Expanding the evaluation of Audio to Score Matching applying Audio Querying strategies

Iván Fernández Cocaño

Supervisor: Alia Morsi

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Abstract

Audio to Score matching, the task of matching an audio query with a particular audio sample in a database, is topic of interest in the Music Information Retrieval (MIR) field. This line of investigation does not have many of works and in those works, there are many differences in the evaluation strategies. An expansion and exploration of new evaluation metrics to comprehend this field is needed to progress.

This research explores the interconnections of audio to score matching with related fields such as Audio Score Alignment (ASA), Cover Identification, and Query-By-Humming (QBH). These similar fields will be grouped and referred to as audio querying in this thesis. Through this lens, the objective is to understand the evaluation strategies in these lines of investigation and utilize them to gain insights into how to expand audio to score matching evaluation.

This thesis's core is the proposition of an expansion of audio matching evaluation strategies, addressing the current lack of standardized practices. A Python implementation of these metrics is provided. All code developed is part of this thesis.

The experiment results show that the proposed metrics reflect how the matching systems perform, and give insight into how they position the correct match overall when experimenting with different songs. This, together with metrics that allow to evaluate how good the systems are at positioning the correct match at the first rank, helps expand the evaluation strategies of audio to score matching. Many more insights can be gained of the data used and its impact in audio to score matching, which will be discussed in detail later on.

Keywords: Audio to Score matching; Audio querying; Evaluation;

Chapter 1

Introduction

Audio to Score matching, is the task of matching an audio query to its corresponding musical score within a database.

Evaluating audio to score matching systems poses unique challenges, hampering the ability to comprehensively assess their performance and compare different approaches. Work in this regard can help expand its evaluation strategies.

1.1 Motivation

Personally, I was driven by my passion for music information retrieval and my interest in understanding current techniques for matching audio with its with their corresponding song to explore this line of work, as I believe that audio to score matching has the potential to be a useful tool in many situations.

Audio to score matching can be a valuable tool, particularly for musicians. The ability to identify the score that a musician is playing from a short excerpt, as demonstrated by Muñoz-Montoro's score identification work [1], can greatly simplify a musician's life by assisting them in finding their music sheets. By contributing to developing audio matching systems, I aspire to impact the music community and enhance musicians' experiences positively.

Currently, there is a lack of a standardized framework for evaluating audio matching

systems. This absence hinders researchers and practitioners from effectively benchmarking and comparing the performance of different methods. Evaluating audio matching systems requires the consideration of various aspects, including accuracy, computational efficiency, robustness to noise and variations, scalability, and usability. This can be seen through most of the works explored in this thesis in audio matching, where evaluation metrics and experiment setups are different and not shared in between works [2, 3, 4, 5, 1]. This is also a problem in Audio to Score Alignment [6] where this lack of defined evaluated frameworks and ground truths of data to test systems also burdens advancement in research.

Expanding the range of possible metrics using metrics from other research fields would enable researchers to expand their evaluation and compare different systems on multiple dimensions, leading to more advancements in the area.

The relevance of this work is in providing new insights into evaluation metrics that can be used for state-of-the-art audio to score matching systems, supported by the most relevant metrics taken from other related fields, such as cover identification, query-by-humming, and audio to score alignment. We will refer to this similar tasks, together with audio to score matching as Audio Querying. Some metrics taken from this audio querying context are:

- MR1 (Mean Reciprocal Rank at the first correct position).
- MRR (Mean Reciprocal Rank).
- P@10
- The mean number of matches identified in the top 10 (average performance):

And they are explained in the State of the Art section2.

With this, research will be able to highlight the strengths and weaknesses of new implementations. This work will also provide a simple Python framework where future matching system implementations can easily "plug in" its results to create

quantitative and qualitative analyses of the outcome of experiments in this field. This work can help inform future research and development and guide the selection of the best method for different musical scenarios.

Figure 1: Example of the information that can be gathered with this framework.

1.2 Objectives

The objectives set for this thesis are:

- Develop an understanding of audio matching and its most relevant research.
- Create an overview of the State of the Art of the related topics to matching, their differences, and how they relate to each other.
- Implement baseline matching implementations from previous relevant works to compare with each other.
- Gather metrics used in Audio Querying and understand how they can be applied here.

- Propose an expansion of the evaluation strategies currently used to evaluate audio matching (MR1, MRR, P@10, Avg. of top 10 matches).
- Show results and how these proposed metrics behave in the experiments.
- Quantitative and qualitative analysis of findings and conclusions of the work: the interesting relations between the used metrics and its limitations regarding the data used in the matching.

1.3 Audio to Score Matching and Related Fields

This thesis will also explore more fields than Audio to Score matching to find the relationships within them and see the benefits that can be taken from these other fields of research into matching. These fields to be explored are Audio to Score Alignment (ASA), which is relevant as it has been used in Audio to Score matching [1], Audio to Score Matching [3, 4, 5, 2, 7, 8], Cover identification [9, 10, 11] and Query-By-Humming (QBH) [12, 13].

Starting with the most similar task, cover identification shares many similarities with Audio to Score matching, making it a great source of inspiration for research in audio matching. The differences between these two tasks lie in that cover identification aims to find when a particular audio recording is a rendition of a specific song. In contrast, audio matching tries to find the closest match between an audio query and a database of audio samples.

Cover identification is important for music organization, retrieval, recommendation, and license management [9]. Query By Humming is also related to the matching problem contemplated in this thesis, as it proposes a music retrieval task of identifying a song from hummed tunes and ASA is also relevant, as it can be used for the task of alignment and it suffers from some problems in its evaluation that are similar to those found in audio to score matching, making knowledge in this field also valuable.

By leveraging the knowledge gained from these research areas, we aim to expand

audio matching evaluation techniques so insights can be gained into how to what metrics can be helpful to expand the current evaluation strategies in audio to score matching. The ultimate goal is to find robust and efficient metrics to evaluate audio-matching systems and accurately give information about different systems' performances.

1.4 Structure of the Report

Table 1: Structure of the thesis.

Content	Summary
Introduction	Brief discussion about the topics this thesis deals with and the motivation behind it.
State of the art	Topics of research investigated to conduct the research, explaining the relations within all fields the obtained evaluation system and the chosen matching implementations.
Methodology	Detailed account of the procedures and techniques used to conduct the research, explaining all decisions taken to design the obtained evaluation system and the chosen matching implementations.
Results and Discussion	Experimental results are organized to show what the research results have led up to, with an interpretation of the results of the research, concluding and discussing the implications of these findings

Chapter 2

State of the Art

Various focus areas have emerged in the rapidly evolving field of music information retrieval, each with its challenges, methodologies, and state-of-the-art solutions. We can find many relations between audio to score matching and different MIR topics that will be reviewed in this section.

2.1 Audio Querying and its similarities

In this thesis we relate the topic of audio to score matching to audio to score alignment (ASA), cover identification, and query by humming. This broad set of research topics is what we have called Audio Querying. We can relate these topics by considering their input, the task they solve and their evaluation strategies. This first section will serve as a broad approach to these fields and their relationship. For a quick summary of the content in this section, Figure 10 provides an overview of these key areas that have been researched, summarizing the central themes in each. As we delve deeper into these areas throughout this thesis, this summary will serve as a guide, grounding our discussion in the context of the broader field.

2.1.1 Input

Audio to Score matching takes an audio recording as a query and it has the task of matching this task to its corresponding score. This could also be done by matching

in other ways, like audio to audio or MIDI to MIDI, but this thesis focuses on audio to score. This input is the same as the one taken in cover identification and query by humming, where a recorded audio is also used, but in this case, of a human-hummed melody. In these three research topics, a database of reference songs will be compared against the input. The case of ASA is a bit different, as the audio recording and the music score you want to compare it to are already known.

2.1.2 Task to solve

For audio matching, cover identification and query by humming the objective is similar: obtain the entry from the database most similar to the input. Going into detail, there are differences, the most obvious being the query by humming case, in which human-made mistakes in tempo and key must be handled [12]. For cover identification, the objective is to identify if the input song is a cover version of any reference songs, which has its legal implications and must consider what is considered a cover song [10]. In the case of audio matching, the task would be to get the score corresponding to the song played in the input [3]. For ASA, the objective would be to map and align audio recordings to the score accurately [14].

ASA might be the most different topic, but it is still interesting to add to this study as it can perform audio to score matching using the similarity scores of alignment [1], making it a relevant research line.

2.1.3 Evaluation strategies

While these fields aren't identical, many of the metrics found in this audio querying group can be modified and applied to evaluate audio to score matching.

Considering that we will have a system that will retrieve a list of the ordered songs, with the most probable score matches in the higher positions, some of the metrics that can be used to evaluate the quality of this output that are seen in many works are:

- MRR: Mean Reciprocal Rank, which allows measuring the ranking effective-

ness of the audio matching system by considering the position of the first correct match. A higher MR1 indicates that the correct match is found in the top candidates more often.

- MR1: Mean Reciprocal Rank at Rank 1. It measures the average effectiveness by considering the positions of all correct matches. A higher MRR is better, as it signifies that the correct matches are found earlier in the ranked list on average.
- P@10: Measures the average capacity of the system in getting the correct match within the top 10 results.

These metrics can provide a comprehensive picture of how effectively an audio-matching algorithm performs in terms of accuracy and ranking efficacy. By considering multiple aspects of the matching task, we can identify the most effective algorithm and highlight specific strengths and weaknesses that might influence their application in real-world scenarios.

Following various works in different parts of the audio querying field [10, 11, 9], evaluation methods like MAP, P@10, and MR1 are used. For audio to score matching, both MR1 and P@10 metrics can be used. The MR1 metric is useful because it measures the system's efficiency by considering the inverse of the rank of the correct match in the list of results. The essence of MR1 lies in its emphasis on the importance of the correct match being at the top of the result list. Essentially, the lower the rank of the correct match (i.e., the closer it is to the top of the list), the higher the MR1 score will be. It gives us a quantitative measure of how often our system gets the match right on the first try.

Alongside MR1, P@10 will be used, which evaluates the system's ability to return relevant items (in this case, correct matches) within the top 10 results. Together, MR1 and P@10 give us a holistic view of our system's performance: MR1 captures the precision of our system in returning the correct match at the top rank, while P@10 sheds light on how frequently the correct match appears within the top 10

ranks. This combined use of MR1 and P@10 provides us with a rigorous and comprehensive evaluation of the system’s retrieval capabilities, considering the precision at the very top rank and the consistency of relevant results within the top 10 positions. This metric is more typical of query by humming or cover identification, but its application in audio to score matching will potentially bring insights about evaluation.

Each topic will have a detailed account of its evaluation strategies in its particular chapter, but this serves as a summary of the most common metrics found and shared between them that can also be applied in audio to score matching.

Again, there is the need to mention that as ASA is not as similar as the other three topics, its evaluation strategies might be different and not applicable to audio to score matching. However, we still can gather knowledge from the problems that ASA is dealing with regarding the need for benchmark scenarios, consolidating evaluation strategies, and considering the different musical scenarios for experimentation [6].

RESEARCH FIELD	INPUT	GOAL	DIFFICULTIES
Audio to Score Alignment	Audio recording and the music score to be aligned to (Usually synthesized MIDI).	Accurately map and align audio recording to the score.	Differences in performance and interpretation. Lack of ground-truth data and benchmarks to test algorithms
Audio to Score matching	Query song and dataset of reference songs. Could be audio to audio, audio to midi matching...	Identifying a given audio recording or music file from a database of songs	Under-researched field with a lack of consensus on evaluation and experimental settings.
Cover identification	Query song and dataset of reference songs	Identify whether the input song is a cover of any of the reference songs	Varied performances and interpretations in cover songs, audio quality differences, different arrangements in cover songs
Query-by-humming	Hummed melody query and dataset of reference songs	Retrieve the hummed song.	Handle human errors: Key mistakes in hummed melody, pitch...

Figure 2: Summary of interconnections in audio matching and related areas.

2.2 Dynamic Time Warping

2.2.1 Algorithm description

Given the relevance of this algorithm in all audio querying fields, except cover identification, where neural networks are more prevalent, it is important to define how DTW works. DTW helps compare features between time sequences (in this case, audio data) to obtain the similarity between them, and in the case of ASA, to perform the alignment. The alignment is performed between two time sequences (in most cases, the obtained features of the input song and an entry of the database that it is compared against. For ASA, just the score you want to align the performance). In this stage, a cost matrix is calculated from the differences in the audio features you want to compare and the input performance to see the similarities between both sounds. After this, DTW is used to generate and find the most optimal path of this cost matrix. First, DTW generates a matrix, D , in this way:

$$D(i, j) = \psi(u_i, v_j)$$

Both series, u and v , represent arrays with the spectral patterns obtained at a point in time. D has $I \times J$ elements representing the cost between every two points in the time series. The cost function could be any function that returns 0 for a perfect match and a positive value otherwise. In the second stage of the alignment, a warping matrix is calculated recursively as:

$$C(i, j) = \min \begin{cases} C(i, j - c_j + D(i, j)) \\ C(i, -c_i, j + D(i, j)) \\ C(i - c_i, j - c_j + \sigma D(i, j)) \end{cases}$$

From this matrix, the optimal path $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k, w_K)$ is obtained using recursion from $C(I, J)$. This path must also follow multiple conditions in its computation; it must be continuous, monotonic, and bounded by the ends of both sequences.

The experiments with this method show very robust results, especially in the offline alignment, in which it outperforms other alignment methods, even when facing polyphonic data.

2.2.2 Optimizing DTW

One of the main drawbacks of this method is its computational cost, which is why it is more fitted to be used in offline characteristics. To calculate the DTW in the usual way, it has a time and space complexity of $O(N^2)$, so its use might be limiting when comparing a series of too big of problem size. There are many proposals to solve this problem, like FastDTW [15], which manages to reduce the cost of this algorithm giving back an accurate approximation of the optimal warp between two series without falling into the brute-force approach of the classic DTW. It manages this through different operations like finding a minimum-distance warp path at a lower resolution that is used as an initial guess for later getting the higher resolution's minimum-distance warp path. This solution reduces DTW's time and space complexity to $O(N)$.

DTW can be made more efficient in matching using techniques like similarity search, which consists of finding similar patterns or sequences in a large dataset using DTW, or pruning and lower-bound distance, which has been used to optimize the DTW search [16]. Nie's study implements both strategies; early abandoning, which aims to reduce the computational cost of DTW by avoiding the total calculation of DTW for candidate sequences so that, when calculating the cumulative distance matrix, when the incremental cost of the optimal warping path gets higher than a set threshold, the calculation of DTW stops.

Lower distance bound is used as an efficient way to quickly estimate the distance between two-time series without performing the full Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) calculation. It is a lower bound on the DTW distance between the two-time series. Different time series can be eliminated from consideration using the lower distance bound, and focus can be put only on the more promising candidate [16, 17].

Adding to these works for making DTW more efficient, Silva proposed a pruning strategy [17] called SS-PrunedDTW based on two stages: an early pruning stage and a late pruning stage. The early pruning stage uses lower bounds to estimate the distance between the query and the candidate time series. The candidate time series can be pruned if the lower bound exceeds the best-so-far (BSF) distance. This reduces the number of DTW distance calculations needed, significantly speeding up the search process. After the early pruning stage, the late pruning stage is done to the remaining candidate time series. The candidate time series and associated lower bounds are stored in a priority queue. The candidate time series with the shortest lower bound is chosen for DTW distance calculation after the lower bounds sort the priority queue. The bsf distance is updated, and the candidate time series is included in the result set if the DTW distance is smaller than the bsf distance. Otherwise, it is eliminated.

2.3 Audio to Score Matching

2.3.1 Problem description

Audio to score matching employs algorithms like DTW to find the most fitting musical score from a database corresponding to a given audio input. Initially, the system computes feature vectors from the input audio. These features can be harmonic, like Constant-Q-Transform (CQT), STFT or Harmonic Pitch Class Profile (HPCP) or of other types like timbral features, such as Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs). With algorithms like DTW the similarity of the features can be compared and used to determine the correct match.

2.3.2 Notable works

Audio to score matching has been addressed in many ways. Hu's work [3] was one of the first comparisons of using different features like chroma, MFCC, pitch histograms, and NMFCC (Normalized MFCC) for the task of matching using DTW. DTW has been used for matching in many other studies [3, 4, 5, 1, 8]. One common

thread in all these studies is that they compute similarity scores using the alignment cost and various types of normalization. Still, as it will be seen, the evaluation strategies and experimentation settings are different in all cases.

A famous example of audio matching (in this case, of audio to audio matching) is audio fingerprinting, a technique which services such as Shazam employ. Audio fingerprinting [18] involves obtaining a set of tokens, known as peaks, from the spectrogram of the queried song. These peaks represent the most distinctive features of the music and are subsequently organized into "constellations" from which a unique hash, called a fingerprint, can be created. The fingerprints are then compared to a database that stores the same features of all possible matches, with the closest match being proposed as the identification of the input audio. This algorithm only works for matching exact copies of the input signal in the database, so it is irrelevant in our score matching problem, as the peaks obtained from recorded performances will not be exact enough to compare to the synthesized MIDI versions obtained from the data used. Other ways must be used for audio to score matching.

An approach that works for as a base for the developed matching system is the one like Hu uses [3], where he creates a system capable of performing audio to score matching, which follows this diagram:

Figure 3: Diagram of audio to score matching system.

This system works by synthesizing the MIDI scores and then storing the features

of each song in a database. These features are then compared against the input's features using DTW. A list of the songs ordered by similarity to the input is returned. After having this system ready, Hu runs an experiment evaluated in 2 steps. The first compares the features using 10 acoustic recordings of Beatles' songs as queries and their corresponding MIDI audio files as targets. The results are evaluated by counting the number of times the correct file is obtained as the first result and with the mean reciprocal rank (MRR) of the results. A second experiment uses 51 acoustic recordings as queries and 259 midi files as targets. To visualize the distribution of the experiment, a pie chart is created showing the rank of correct matches, plotting categories if the correct result ranks 1, 2, 3, 4-5,6-10, 11-259.

Raffel [4] proposed a convolutional neural network that can hash both the midi and audio CQT extracted features to a common representation in Hamming space; the Hamming space is used to reduce the dimensionality of the CQT (Constant-Q Transform) features used to represent the MIDI and audio data. The CQT features are first transformed into binary codes using a hashing function. These binary codes are then mapped to a Hamming space, a space of binary vectors where the distance between two vectors is measured by the number of bits that differ between them. Raffel creates a dataset of MIDI files scrapped from the internet aligned to its corresponding songs obtained from the Million Song Dataset (MSD). By mapping the binary codes to a Hamming space, the feature vectors' dimensionality is reduced, making it more efficient to perform large-scale dynamic time-warping searches. This is because the Hamming distance between two binary vectors can be computed quickly using bitwise operations, making it possible to search for matches between MIDI and audio data in real time. This evaluation uses a set of known MIDI-MSD matches to have a groundtruth from which the performance can be measured. The results show that this system works better as a pruning method as it can filter songs most of the songs that are not similar to the target one from the Million Song Dataset. Still, it lacks the accuracy to obtain the correct song in the first position.

Ens follows this work [8] and works further on it using more efficient C++ code for the DTW and a similar neural network for calculating the hashes. This system

proves to be faster than the calculated DTW from the full features. Still, as seen in Raffel's work [4], it proves to be more of a pruning tool to get a subset of similar matches that can then be aligned using DTW on its full features than to determine the actual match. In this case, the evaluation was performed using different audio sources with metadata obtained from web scrapping to create a ground truth in which the percentage of songs that have been matched can be presented.

2.4 Cover identification

2.4.1 Problem description

Cover Identification refers to the process of recognizing a rendition of a known song that has been reinterpreted or covered by a different artist. Unlike the original, these covers can possess distinct rhythm, tempo, and instrumentation variations. The primary challenge in this domain is identifying and matching songs based on their core melodic structure, even when faced with significant stylistic deviations.

Much like Query By Humming, which matches a hummed melody to a database, Cover Identification requires searching for a known pattern within a larger musical dataset. However, while Query By Humming focuses on approximations of melodies, Cover Identification deals with fully produced musical tracks.

2.4.2 Notable works

Some approaches in this field like the one done by Du in his Bytecover cover identification via multi-loss training [9] uses CNN trained methods in which a neural network is trained to classify music tracks extracting a single global feature that encodes the version information. When comparing these features using Cosine distance, one can determine how similar these tracks are, and if one is a version of the other. In this work, various available benchmark datasets used for cover identification are used, like Youtube350, Covers80 and Da-TACOS.

To evaluate the obtained results, many different metrics are used like mean average

precision (MAP), Precision at 10 (P@10) and Mean Reciprocal Rank at Rank 1 (MR1). From these metrics, the ones that seem more applicable for Audio to Score matching are MR1 and P@10 as they quite easy to integrate with the results obtained from our score matching systems and they will help determine the performance.

Another work that uses a NNs was made by Yesiler [11], who created a model to encode entire recordings into plain vector embeddings that can then be compared. For the performed evaluation of his experiment, he also uses MAP and MR1.

For more evaluation inspiration, one could take a look into the latest MIREX challenge for Cover Identification (MIREX¹) entry for Audio Cover Song Identification in 2021, there was a proposal for an evaluation of the cover recognition systems. In MIREX, cover system evaluations utilized metrics such as the total covers identified in the top 10, the average number of covers positioned in the top 10, and the arithmetic mean of Avg. Precisions and the mean rank of the first correctly identified covers.

Another way of doing cover song identification is through the use of local like self-similarities of MFCC-based features. This can be seen in Tralie’s model [19] which shows much better performance in cover identification than just using plain MFCC features. In this case, for evaluation purposes Tralie uses mean rank (MR), MRR, and the number of times that the correct cover was identified in the top position (Top-01) and in the first 10 positions (Top-10) showing the performance of Hu’s system in audio to score matching.

2.5 Query By Humming

2.5.1 Problem description

Query By Humming presents the task of matching a hummed melody by a human to a database [12]. It has to deal with numerous problems that come from human input, like hummed queries that use the wrong tempo or key.

¹https://www.music-ir.org/mirex/wiki/2021:Audio_Cover_Song_Identification

2.5.2 Notable works

One of the most cited works in this field is by Kosugi, [12], who created a system to search for a song in a database of over 10000 songs composed of standard pop MIDI transcribed songs. This work uses 186 performed queries to evaluate the system. It uses different rank position results for the query, its corresponding song, and the number of matches in that rank to show how the proposed system performs. This shows how it is essential to consider when a match is in a higher position. When comparing results, it is important to consider more than just retrieving when the match is positioned in the first result.

Putri proposes a system that uses DTW [13] to search for Indonesian songs stored in a MIDI format, comparing audio features of the database with a human-hummed input. It uses subsequence DTW, which tries to find the input as a subsequence of the template for all songs in the database. It uses a confidence score that determines how confident the input can be recognized as a certain song.

We can obtain insights into the evaluation used for a system like this, as it is quite similar to audio to score, in which you also have to find a certain score from a database. To evaluate the results, Putri uses two metrics: reciprocal rank and mean reciprocal rank, which allows to an evaluation of the system by taking into account the position of the results, giving higher scores to results in the higher positions.

2.6 Audio to Score Alignment

2.6.1 Problem definition

Audio-to-score alignment refers to the process of synchronizing a given audio recording to its corresponding musical score. The relevance of this topic in this thesis is that ASA can actually be used to perform the task of audio to score matching, as done by Muñoz-Montoro [1]. Knowing the different types of alignment might benefit the research and inspire new ideas of where the evaluation strategies might be lacking like it might happen in ASA [6].

This task has a diverse range of approaches on how to perform the actual alignment, so, to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of this task in the field of MIR, each of these methods can be classified in four areas: as knowledge-driven, which incorporates data derived from the sound's characteristics; stochastic, which employs Hidden Markov Models (HMM) to accommodate for acoustic variations and temporal fluctuations; data-driven, which utilizes machine learning and AI methods to perform an alignment and hybrid, which mixes data-driven with other approaches.

This categorization of the state-of-the-art approaches to ASA is derived from the work conducted by Agrawal in [20]. To provide a comprehensive understanding of the current state-of-the-art for each category of ASA, this section will be subdivided into dedicated subsections, each offering an in-depth explanation of the latest advances in that specific category of ASA.

2.6.2 Knowledge driven: Dynamic Time Warping

One of the traditional methods used in audio to score alignment is Dynamic Time Warping (DTW). DTW is an algorithm used to find similarities between two temporal sequences of different speeds. It has been proposed many times for the task of ASA, for example, in Dixon's work in [21], where it was first proposed as a method for tracking in an online way the performances of musicians or Carabias-Orti's proposal [14] for an ASA that performed well in both offline and online applications.

Works like the one from Raffel [5] offer a "gold-standard" version of DTW with fine tuning of its many different parameters easily accessible for any researchers to have access to a really optimized version of the algorithm.

2.6.3 Stochastic approach: Hidden Markov Models

One of the conventional techniques for aligning audio to score is Hidden Markov Model (HMMs). Numerous approaches have been proposed for addressing this problem using HMMs. For instance, Nakamura's work [22] introduced a model that aims to track audio performances that involve repetitions and omissions, typical issues a

learning performer encounters. This model exclusively applies to monophonic performances and deals with all acoustic variations and temporal fluctuations within the HMM model by employing different states and transitions between them. The primary focus of this model is on performance, thereby avoiding complexity issues that arise if all top states of the HMM are required to describe the arbitrary problems. This is achieved by constraining the HMM in multiple ways, such as assuming that the probability of score positions where performers pause before repeats and omissions are identical, regardless of where they resume their performance.

2.6.4 Data driven

Data-driven approaches leverage the vast amounts of available data to train models that can learn and adapt to complex and dynamic environments. Unlike knowledge-driven systems, data-driven methods use the inherent patterns and relationships within the data to inform the learning process. This allows them to uncover hidden patterns and relationships that may not have been apparent through prior knowledge. Neural networks have seen increased use in audio-to-score alignment works [20, 23, 24, 25], learning complex relationships between audio and score data to predict alignments. They have shown promising results and offer more flexibility in modeling complex musical structures, making them a powerful tool in this and many music information retrieval tasks.

This neural network method has been recently proposed for audio-to-score alignment, showing quite promising results in the work of Agrawal [20], who offers both a hybrid solution and a complete neural network solution for the problem of alignment using a Siamese Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). This CNN is used to introduce a metric that evaluates the similarity between two frames of audio data. The alignment path between the audio and score representations is then created using this metric. Two or more identical subnetworks with the same parameters and were trained on the same task can be found in this network architecture. Compared to the more traditional feature-based approaches, this suggested neural network approach shows increased accuracy, efficiency, and ability to work even with sparse

training data.

Neural Networks are not the only data-driven approach in the alignment field. There are also ways of aligning using the image domain, which can be found in the works of Dorfer [23], [24]. His work focuses on this image domain, where a NN is trained using examples of audio and sheet music pairs to learn how these two elements relate. This model will be able to map these pairs into a shared embedding space, where similar pairs are located close to each other, making it able to perform the task of aligning an audio recording with its corresponding sheet music image and retrieving the correct score from an excerpt of a few seconds.

2.6.5 Hybrid approach

The effort to transition from a complete data-driven approach using Neural Networks or similar AI methods is difficult given the lack of datasets and the current difficulties found in the research in ASA [6]. There have been many proposals, like the ones in [26, 27] that use traditional methods mixed with a more data-driven step for preprocessing, which show the promising results of the previously discussed complete data-driven approaches.

Agrawal’s work in [26] shows an alignment framework proposal in which DTW is applied, using a new preprocessing step for the data that uses neural networks. This preprocessing is trained, making it a method that can be adapted to many situations given enough data to obtain good results, unlike other DTW-based methods that might require handcrafted features. The NN used is a Siamese Convolutional network trained with different patches from the audio and the synthesized MIDI. This NN is tasked to identify if they “match” or not to differentiate between them. The same author proposes a similar method in [20].

Another method aided by DTW and NN is the one used by Wang [28] to help students to learn piano through an automatic evaluation of their performances. In this work, AMT is used to extract the piano transcription, and then an alignment is performed between this template and the performance input to estimate how well it

performs. The model uses convolutional neural networks to extract acoustic features and then align them using DTW.

Chapter 3

Methodology

The primary objective of this master's thesis is to expand on the evaluation strategies employed in the domain of audio-to-score matching within Music Information Retrieval (MIR). By delving into multiple evaluation methodologies of audio querying and extracting the potential applicability of their evaluation strategies and how they behave in varied musical contexts. The research seeks to understand if the chosen metrics truly provide clarity about the performance nuances of various audio to score matching systems.

To do this, experiments using various datasets have been set up with an implementation of audio to score matching. There are two main scenarios that will be tested:

- Classical music context (Musicnet Dataset)
- Multi-genre context (Subset of Lakh Dataset)

From this is expected is that the results in classical music are good when using harmonic features, which provide a representation that mirrors how listeners perceive and differentiate pieces based on harmony. Lower results are expected when comparing it in a multi-genre context, as it has songs that have content that might make

the harmonic features worse in representing it's actual content, such as electronic music with non-tonal information.

3.1 Matching audio and score

To match audio and scores, information about both the score and audio must be extracted to then be compared. The different features that will be used and compared against each other are:

- CQT
- STFT Chromagrams
- CQT Chromagrams
- HPCP

To fine-tune the parameter selection of these features, a hyperparameter search will be done for each metric. Using an expansion of evaluation metrics coming from the audio querying field (MR1, MRR, P@10, Mean number of matches identified in the top 10.) will be applied in these experiments to measure its results. From the comparison within all features it is expected to gain insight into how meaningful the expansion of new metrics are to provide information about the system's performance.

The information gathered from these metrics can be used with DTW to accomplish the task of audio to score matching. The diagram of how the proposed system works will be described and explained in the next section, taking the opportunity to also introduce the modular architecture of the implementation.

Besides an analysis of the proposed evaluation metrics, this work takes into account that evaluation is a complex task and that is necessary to also analyze the results obtained in a more qualitative way, so for this study quantitative and qualitative analysis will be done.

Figure 4: Representation of Chromagrams, HPCP, CQT and STFT features.

3.2 Data used

Two different datasets will be used to perform matching. The datasets are organized in two different folders, each containing the respective synthesized midi files and the recordings of the songs.

Musicnet [29] is a collection of 330 classical music recordings with corresponding files containing the interpreted pieces translated into .mid files. As its data can be filtered and easily organized thanks to the available metadata of each composition, it is doable to divide it and get a different subset of ensembles of music featuring solo piano, solo violin, polyphonic pieces, and many more, which can allow to create different scenarios for experimenting with the different matching approaches within this dataset. This metadata will be leveraged to perform a qualitative analysis of the results, which will allow us to tell in which cases the matching performs better or worse.

The Lakh MIDI dataset [7] will also be used to test music styles other than classical. This dataset comprises 176,581 different MIDI files, of which 45,129 have been

Table 2: All different ensembles and number of compositions in MusicNet

Ensemble	Number of compositions
Accompanied Cello	7
Accompanied Clarinet	4
Accompanied Violin	22
Clarinet Quintet	3
Clarinet-Cello-Piano Trio	3
Horn Piano Trio	4
Pairs Clarinet-Horn-Bassoon	6
Piano Quartet	8
Piano Quintet	4
Piano Trio	7
Solo Cello	12
Solo Flute	3
Solo Piano	156
Solo Violin	9
String Quartet	57
String Sextet	5
Viola Quintet	1
Violin and Harpsichord	4
Wind Octet	4
Wind Quintet	9
Wind and Strings Octet	2

matched and aligned to the Million Song Dataset entries. This will allow testing of the matching systems in a non-classical music environment. For the use of this data for matching, access was made available to the mp3 excerpts of the subset of the Lakh-Midi Dataset matched to songs in the Million Song Dataset [30]. Having access to both MIDI and proper song versions of the songs, using the most probable matches made by Colin Raffel, a new environment has been created to test this subset of audio/midi to test the matching. After getting only the files with the most probable matches and their corresponding midis, the subset of data available for testing is over 2000. Since all matched scores/songs belong to the million song dataset, a varied dataset, we know that in contrast to Musicnet, this subset of data is much more diverse in its musical content, giving us a more complex situation in which to test audio to score matching. This is expected to be reflected in the results.

3.3 Experiment scenarios

This section will outline the experiment scenarios designed to assess the effectiveness of the implemented audio to score matching system.

As explained before, by conducting experiments in multiple scenarios, we aim to identify the most effective techniques for audio matching in different musical contexts while also providing insights into the strengths and weaknesses of each approach.

3.3.1 Feature selection

To begin with, to determine which feature of the audio to use, a comparison between the accuracy of CQT, STFT chroma, CQT chroma, and HPCP features will be made by running the matching experiment many times to compare the obtained results with the evaluation strategy defined in the next section. In previous works like [3], chromagram features were seen as the best option for the matching job, but in others, [5], CQT features were proven to work best. The reason for using chroma (or chromagram) features is that since MIDI data is being compared to acoustic, it is good to focus on the pitch classes and put less weight on factors like timbre and spectral shape, so this type of feature should work well in the first experiment with a classical music context and with the synthesized scores that will be used to compare against real-life recorded audios.

3.3.2 Hyperparameters

Together with the feature selection, to test the impact of variables like the hop length and the frame size, the baseline DTW will be tested by changing the frame and hop length and comparing the obtained results. This will allow us to find the best parameters for each feature.

3.3.3 Efficiency in DTW

This work will implement two different approaches of DTW to explore how efficiency methods impact in audio to score matching:

1. DTW using average distance along the path as the distance measure (Base-DTW). [3].
2. DTW with early abandoning(EA-DTW). [16]

Early abandoning strategy can be described as follows [16]: When calculating the accumulated cost in the cumulative distance matrix, once every element in the g -th row is more significant than a certain threshold, we can infer that there is no need to calculate the rest elements as it will only end as a higher cost than this set threshold.

Librosa's DTW does not implement either early abandoning or lower distance bound, so it will be implemented in its code following a similar process as the algorithm described in Silva's work [16].

3.3.4 Evaluation and running times

To determine the effectiveness of the audio-matching approaches, the evaluation will focus on two main criteria: accuracy and computation time. As for the accuracy, the previously discussed metrics will be used to evaluate the results of the experiments.

Also, given the relevance of the scalability and performance that this task faces, the running time of all the methods using excerpts of 1, 5, 15, and 30 seconds.

3.4 Evaluation assesment

As mentioned before, there is not an evident evaluation standardized approach in the matching papers evaluated [1, 3, 7] that could be used to evaluate systems used in different settings, so to expand the evaluation process, we are taking the most appropriate methods from audio querying sources discussed in the State of the Art.

After adopting these metrics to the matching task, the evaluated system can be measured using:

- MR1 (Mean Reciprocal Rank at the first correct position). A high percentage here indicates that the system prioritizes the most appropriate match for the

input. It's a straightforward but powerful indicator of the system's ability to correctly rank the most relevant match as its top result.

- MRR (Mean Reciprocal Rank). A high percentage here indicates that the system prioritizes the most appropriate match for the input. It's a straightforward but powerful indicator of the system's ability to correctly rank the most relevant match as its top result.
- P@10 (Total number of correct matches positioned in the top 10): A higher total number signifies a robust ranking capability of the system. It is valuable to gauge the system's capacity to identify matches and rank them effectively.
- The mean number of matches identified in the top 10 (average performance): This is calculated as the average number of correct matches found in the top 10 results across all cases. This average performance measure can provide a more stable estimate of the system's performance by reducing the impact of outliers.

Several iterations will be done of the different matching frameworks with random songs from the various subsets of data, and the results will be gathered to visualize the evaluated results in a table. It will provide valuable insights into their performance in other contexts.

These evaluation criteria will enable us to gain insights into the effectiveness of each matching approach and compare their strengths and weaknesses in different musical contexts.

3.5 Code structure

The provided code for this thesis constructs an approach to match audio to scores, drawing on the principle of Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) to gauge similarity. It has been implemented considering all previously discussed topics about evaluation, the data that will be used, and how it should be evaluated and saved. All code is

available publicly in a github repository¹

It has been created using object-oriented programming, starting with a `DTWMatcher` class. It can be followed as a pattern to create audio to score matching software, as you could override the functions you want to change. Here lies the implementation that made possible all the tests. The main functionality of this code lies in:

3.5.1 DTWMatcher Class

The core of the code is encapsulated within this class, designed to house methods related to DTW-based audio to score matching. On instantiation, a database of features extracted from the datasets audios is taken and later used to match. All the following functions are used within this class.

Feature Extraction (`extract_features` method): This method extracts various audio features from a given audio, namely constant-Q transform (CQT), CQT Chroma, SFTFFT chroma, and Harmonic-Pitch Class Profile (HPCP). Default parameters like sample rate, FFT window size, and stride are set but can be modified.

Database Creation Functions (`create_database`): These are designed to build a features database from .wav or .mp3 audio files. The function iterates through a specified folder, loading each audio file, extracting its features, and storing them in a dictionary with an associated ID.

DTW Calculation (`compute_dtw` method): Using `librosa`, it computes the DTW between the extracted audio features and score features, returning both the DTW matrix and the optimal warping path. DTW is an algorithm that can be subtly modified to optimize the results for a specific task. One could, for example, add weights to penalize specific steps or add global constraints for the computation of the warp path, like the Sakoe-Chiba band. Hu [3] does not get involved in any of these methods and prefers to keep the implementation of DTW simple. For this reason, this will serve as the baseline implementation of audio matching using DTW, from which other more efficient methods will be compared. For this implementation

¹<https://github.com/iferco/DTWMatcher/>

of DTW, the Python library of Librosa has been used [31].

Average Distance (average_distance method) and Score Normalization (dtw_score_norm_l2 method): It calculates the average distance of the optimal warping path in the DTW matrix, providing a quantitative measure of the similarity between the audio and score. This similarity method is used in some audio matching works [3]. For the other function, the alignment score is also normalized using the L2 norm, giving a relative sense of similarity for some works[5].

The average distance between the features is used to obtain a similarity measure between the compared features, as a low average distance along the alignment path is expected when matching similar audio. This middle distance provides an intuitive and effective way to quantify the degree of similarity between the two sequences as taking the average (i.e., total distance divided by the length of the alignment path) rather than the sum helps to normalize the measure, making it less dependent on the size of the sequences or the alignment path and lower distances will of course, indicate that the match is much more probable.

Score Identification (identify_score method): This is the main method where given audio is matched against all features in the database using DTW. It returns a list of tuples containing score IDs and their average distances to the input audio frame. The lower the distance, the higher the likelihood of the match.

This code provides a structured framework to facilitate audio-to-score matching, pivoting on DTW's computational efficiency and robustness. The matching process consists of comparing the features extracted from the database to the input audio's features, getting a sorted list of the most similar results as the output of the matching execution.

3.5.2 Data organization

To store the data and process it, we have separated it into two folders. This structure is followed in both the MusicNet and subset of the Lakh Dataset:

The data is divided into two folders: a score folder containing all synthesized versions of the scores and another one with all the performances of those scores. With this structure, random playings of the score can be grabbed and compared against the whole database to perform the audio to score matching task. Auxiliary functions are created in the `utils.py` code to help with this task and be able to work with the stored data to do the experiments efficiently. Many functions are available that are aided by Musicnet's metadata to gather any composition with its corresponding ID and easily find the corresponding score, making it easy to determine the correct match when doing the experiments. Functions similar to these are created for the lakh subset to perform the experiments with the same ease and save time when processing file paths. All functions have their corresponding docstring explaining their use.

There are also two scripts uploaded to help reorganize the MusicNet dataset into a structure that works with all implemented functions. There is no need for this in the case of Lakh as it is much more straightforward.

3.5.3 Evaluation

All functions stored in `eval.py` contain the code used to go from the results of each experiment, which consist of a list containing the number of position of the correct match to all metrics that are used in this experiment.

The functions available are:

- `mean_top_10_pos`: Calculates the average position of all top 10 matches.
- `calculate_p_at_10`: Retrieves P@10 score.
- `calculate_mrr`: Retrieves MRR.
- `calculate_mr1`: Retrieves MR1.
- `get_accuracy`: This function calculates the number of times that the correct composition is in the first position. This metric is not used for the proposed

evaluation strategy, but it is used by Muñoz-Montoro in his work of audio to score matching [1] so it was interesting to implement.

A diagram of the implemented's system structure, showing that to perform the alignment we could use several types of algorithms, such as DTW or SW (Smith Waterman):

Figure 5: Audio to score matching system overview.

Chapter 4

Results and discussion

In this chapter, we present the practical outcomes of our research, looking at how the proposed metrics can evaluate the behavior of matching systems. In this section many examples obtained from the experimentation will be used, they are all available in an open-access Google Drive folder folder¹, the link can also be accessed in the appendix.

First, the results for the MusicNet dataset will be analyzed.

4.1 MusicNet dataset

For measuring how the matching implementation done here behaves, two experiments have been done, one in which a random song is taken and matched against the whole dataset 100 times to gather results in which to apply the proposed metrics. After this, a qualitative analysis is done, in which the matching is done for every file to see where the system might have more problems in matching and try to understand why, aiding ourselves from the metadata contained in this dataset.

¹https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/111FbJWvvGWkHV8b31iY-M5NmJpNzbf_c

4.1.1 Quantitative analysis

Like it is explained in the methodology, the experiment is performed in 4 steps, each using different excerpts of duration for the songs (1, 5, 15, 30) from which different features are extracted and then compared; the metrics are averaged for all the iterations of the experiment. The impact of the length of the audio is clear in the results showed, this is because the longer the audio excerpt, the more broader is the information of the piece contained in that excerpt. This is really important as the matching is done using DTW, so the bigger data, the cost will be exponentially bigger. With one second, the information is too limited and many nuances such as melodies are lost (In some cases the piece does not have time to even start). The key here is to find the balance in between loading the whole song and just a too-short excerpt. What is found in this study is that, at least for this classical music context, with 30 seconds, there is enough development of the musical content to perform the matching correctly. One thing to note, is that this experiment has been repeated numerous times with different hyperparameters value for each feature, what is shown here are the best results found from all those experimentations.

Table 3: MusicNet: Results for 1-second excerpts.

Feature	MR1	MRR	P@10	Avg of top 10 matches
CQT Chroma	0.02	0.05	0.11	3.54
CQT	0.01	0.04	0.09	2.56
STFT Chroma	0.05	0.07	0.1	0.7
HPCP	0.05	0.08	0.14	1.93

Table 4: MusicNet: Results for 5-second excerpts.

Feature	MR1	MRR	P@10	Avg of top 10 matches
CQT Chroma	0.34	0.42	0.57	1.39
CQT	0.18	0.23	0.32	2.0
STFT Chroma	0.18	0.30	0.53	1.98
HPCP	0.06	0.11	0.22	2.95

Table 5: MusicNet: Results for 15-second excerpts.

Feature	MR1	MRR	P@10	Avg of top 10 matches
CQT Chroma	0.78	0.84	0.93	0.34
CQT	0.25	0.34	0.93	0.34
STFT Chroma	0.59	0.69	0.87	0.90
HPCP	0.22	0.32	0.53	2.45

Table 6: MusicNet: Results for 30-second excerpts.

Feature	MR1	MRR	P@10	Avg of top 10 matches
CQT Chroma	0.93	0.95	0.97	0.103
CQT	0.3	0.38	0.54	1.6
STFT Chroma	0.84	0.905	0.93	0.232
HPCP	0.37	0.47	0.65	0.47

These results show how the metrics behave as expected with the presented features. As the previous tables show, chromagrams are the best resulting features in all experiments. In the 15 and 30-second experiments, some metrics almost reached a near-perfect score, showing excellent behavior in this dataset.

This is because chromagrams are a way of representing data that focuses on capturing tonal information, making them especially valuable in a context like this one (classical music) in which the harmonic and tonal features of the audio signal are rich and allow the harmonic features to contain meaningful information that allows to perform the matching. Another bonus of these chromagrams is that they reduce dimensionality compared to the full STFT or CQT computation, which is very valuable when using DTW to align the results. This aligns with the results in all tables, in which we see that the CQT results have a worse outcome than the Chroma CQT or Chroma STFT ones.

When using CQT or STFT chroma, the retrieved matches are in the top 1 result in most cases (This is because of the close to 1.0 result in MR1) while failing on some occasions, but most of the time, the result is in the top 10, which is reflected in

that the average of top 10 matches rank will be close to 0 (Avg of top 10 matches). When you compare this to the results of the plain CQT, one can see how the metrics reflect that the matching is much more successful in these chroma-type features, which makes sense in the current musical context of the MusicNet dataset.

These results can be compared with previous works, as this dataset has been used before in audio to score matching. Muñoz-Montoro used this dataset [1], although focusing only on spectral features. He found great results with his work, in which he only measured accuracy as the % of times that the queried item was found in the first item. The most similar metric to the one in our proposed evaluation strategy expansion would be MR1, where similar results are observed.

Our metrics show similar performance on average, but using all metrics together helps us piece together insights about problems that might be invisible otherwise, like the existence of outliers. This can be seen by comparing two metrics used, P@10 and MRR. Let's take, for example, the results of HPCP or plain CQT for 30-second excerpts. In this case, the P@10 is a significantly higher value than the MRR. What this allows us to tell is that our system can match the song to the correct score in more than half of the cases, but even though this happens, the MRR is relatively low, meaning that those songs that are not correctly matched are lost in the low ranks of the list, making the MRR score worse. This helps us determine that our system has trouble with some of the songs that can't correctly match their score using these features. From this information, a qualitative analysis can be done of these mismatched scores to find if there is any pattern that justifies why the matching is not properly working in these cases: a qualitative analysis.

4.1.2 Qualitative analysis

Now, every song will be tested and matched against the dataset. With the data from all these matches, a box and violin plot will be created to gain insights into why some songs perform better than others using the metadata available in Musicnet. With this qualitative analysis, we can focus on which songs show more difficulty in the matching process and why.

Figure 6: MRR boxplot using all features.

These plots show how the results in Chroma for the Mean Reciprocal Rank are mostly higher than 0.6, with a few outliers outside of that rank. The median is at the top for CQT Chroma and STFT Chroma, showing that higher values are more common in both these features (The higher density in the violin plot can also tell this). For CQT chroma, something hidden in the previous average result table can be observed: the values are mostly either at the top or low; this is why the interquartile range reaches the whole MRR range of values in the graph. This means the CQT chroma gets lost in some songs while performing perfectly for others. This also matches what was observed in the relation between the MRR and P@10 metrics.

When checking the songs with the lowest MRRs and leveraging this database's metadata, it can be noticed that most of these songs are highly tempo (allegro) songs, which might confuse the chromagram as the rapid succession of notes and the reduced time available to accurately analyze and represent the harmonic content

Figure 7: MRR boxplot using all features.

within each time frame might affect the accuracy. It also might be related that these failed songs are mostly polyphonic ensembles of string instruments, presenting even more difficulties to the chromagram representation. Some of these examples, both the easy and challenging matches, have been uploaded in the drive folder previously mentioned.

4.1.3 Performance analysis

To evaluate the system's performance, we have taken the average execution times of performing the score matching process with each feature 100 times. As expected, we can see that the longer the audio excerpt is taken, the longer it takes to calculate it. We can also see that CQT takes much longer to compute than the other metrics, which makes sense as CQT vectors would be longer than chromagram vectors (12 values for chromagrams vs. potentially hundreds for CQT), DTW would naturally take longer with raw CQT features.

Figure 8: Execution times for matching with each feature.

This next figure shows the impact of early abandoning in the execution times:

Figure 9: Comparison between DTW and Early Abandoning DTW.

As can be seen, the more significant difference is found in STFT chromagrams,

where 2 seconds can be saved. Meanwhile, for CQT chromagrams, only a little over 0.20 seconds are saved. In this case, it is hard to justify early abandoning as it doesn't show much improvement time-wise and it can affect the accuracy of the matching. Given that this system works already with excerpts of sounds, the size of the series of data that are being compared using DTW is not that big, so early abandoning might not give that much of an advantage compared to the regular algorithm. This method would probably be helpful if we compared the whole songs, as much more time would be saved on average by exiting the song earlier. This doesn't mean that further optimizations of DTW shouldn't be researched, as maybe using some pruning to remove the most non-similar matches from entering the DTW stage could be another way of upgrading performance, as discussed by Raffel in his work for large-content matching using MIDI [4].

4.2 Lakh Aligned dataset

This dataset allows for experimenting with audio to score matching with different music genre content. With over 2000 files and their corresponding MIDI scores, experiments in this dataset will give us good insights into how our metrics behave.

4.2.1 Quantitative analysis

Because of the difficulties this new dataset generates in this genre-varied musical context, meaningful results are only obtained when using CQT and STFT chromagrams and 30-second excerpts.

Table 7: Lakh Aligned: Results for 30-second excerpts.

Feature	MR1	MRR	P@10	Avg of top 10 matches
CQT Chroma	0.46	0.52	0.63	1.08
STFT Chroma	0.12	0.15	0.2	1.5

These results show that the CQT and STFT chroma perform significantly worse in this context than in the MusicNet Dataset, especially the STFT chroma. This

makes sense as CQT is a feature thought to represent musical information compared to STFT, which might contain more information irrelevant to the matching that might confuse the chromagram and, therefore, the resulting DTW alignment.

4.2.2 Qualitative analysis

Given the dimensions of the data here, it is difficult to perform a qualitative analysis of each song like it was done in the MusicNet dataset, as we have almost ten times more data in this subset of the Lakh Dataset, it would take too much time to perform the analysis with each song of the dataset. Despite this, we can look into some pieces that perform poorly. One example of these songs is Adivinha by Os Travessos, a track from a samba group from Brazil that contains a really noisy sound of people partying and shouting with a background saxophone. In the case of the MIDI, the sounds of people are not reflected, containing only the saxophone melody, which makes the matching almost impossible with the resulting noise affecting the features that DTW will use to compare. This means that the correct score ends up poorly positioned.

Even knowing that there are some cases in which the harmonic features get lost, something that must be considered is that an advantage of using these types of features is that when comparing songs performed by different ensembles of instruments and performances, the matching does still work. This was tested using various versions from the Internet of people playing Bach's Cello Suite 3, Prelude performing the matching against the whole dataset. Our system can still return the correct result in the first place, even though each performance might have unique differences. Even when another instrument, like a piano, plays the piece, the harmonic content is similar, and the DTW does not get lost when performing the alignment and can return the correct piece.

Figure 10: Comparison between extracted features of audio and synthesized MIDI.

Another thing that can be observed from the use of this dataset is that a lot of the electronic songs are hard to match using the current features and end up affecting the average of the metrics (after performing a genre classification of our subset of Lakh with an Essentia model, electronic was the second most common genre). This shows how vital the content to be analyzed is when designing the matching system, as harmonic features are not the best choice for audio with less tonal content.

4.3 Conclusions

We can gain many insights from the experimentation and analyses performed for this thesis. By assessing various metrics' proficiency in evaluating audio-matching results, this research has shed light on the relationships, efficiencies, and potential shortcomings in the studied metrics.

What is found with this expansion of evaluation strategies, is that only using one metric, like MRR or some sort of precision on average for audio to score matching might not be enough to correctly measure how one system behaves. Using more metrics like is proposed here, gives us insights that might be lost otherwise and shows the need of not only performing an on average analysis, but to qualitative analyze the obtained results. In this way, we can conclude that there are benefits from using the expanded metrics proposed and that it is also essential to perform a

qualitative analysis when possible, to get the full picture. This expansion of metrics is able to give a more complete view of audio to score matching evaluation, closer to how audio cover identification and query by humming evaluates, as these fields also use multiple metrics to extract insights about their systems' performance.

4.3.1 Discussion

The relationship between MRR and P@10 that has been observed regarding the used metrics, allows us to tell information from the data that using those isolated metrics would not directly tell, it allowed to tell the existence of certain outliers in all features. MR1 and MRR act as relevant metrics, MR1 being vital if you want to consider only correct results as those in the first rank, and MRR is helpful to be able to weigh in how good is, in general, the system in placing the proper match towards the top. One metric from this proposed expansion that does not show relevant information is the average rank of the top 10 matches, as it does not provide any insights that might be key to reading into the results, the information that it conveys can be found in MR1.

As for the features used, which are only harmonic, the results solidly established that chromagrams, specifically the CQT Chroma, are particularly apt for evaluating audio to score matching in the context of classical music. They capture such compositions' intricate tonal and harmonic characteristics, outperforming direct spectral representations like plain CQT. This might not be the best in all scenarios, as noticed by the worst performance in the Lakh subset. This means that when facing audio to score matching, one should consider the scenario and musical context of the data to match and select metrics that allow for better results. In some cases, harmonic features might not be the answer, and other features like timbral features such as MFCC should be considered.

The datasets used in experimentation also provide us with various musical contexts that can lead us to some conclusions for audio to score matching; something fundamental is that the data used in this task is essential for the decisions you make when designing the audio to score matching system. These experiments show that

it is impossible to create a audio to score matching system capable of performing matching in a general way - music in its many different contexts offers too much of a nuance between genres to work correctly. One should, instead, focus on applying the correct approach to the given data. There seems to be no one-size-fits-all approach to this task, at least with this approach. The variability in performance across different musical contexts underscores the necessity of a tailored approach based on the nature of the data. Recognizing the right features and metrics for a given dataset remains pivotal.

4.3.2 Future work

Further work could be done in various areas to advance research on this topic. More research could be done into how the proposed evaluation expansion behaves using more features that are not harmonic. This would also allow us to analyze in which cases each feature type should be used to solve the audio to score matching task. This could go together with new datasets, exploring types of features in different musical contexts.

Regarding the alignment algorithm, DTW, which has been used frequently in works in this field, a discussion could be opened about the possibility of eschewing the reliance on this algorithm for performing alignment and finding alternatives that might render better results. One could consider other algorithms like Smith-Waterman, more commonly used in Query By Humming, or even going further and using neural networks trained with custom loss functions based on time-series divergences to perform the alignment task between features. Agrawal has recently proposed this in his audio-to-score alignment work [20], and as the two fields are related, it could be applied to this task. This can lead to abandoning DTW or similar audio-to-score matching algorithms, which has still not been explored.

One promising direction that could be interesting for future investigations is using neural networks to learn to distinguish the similarity of the songs and scores, also abandoning traditional features. This is similar to what is currently used in cover identification, where using neural networks to obtain NN-made features that can

then be compared is much more common. With enough data to train it, it might be feasible to create a system to tackle multi-genre audio to score matching. All in all, this shows huge potential that should be considered in future research, as if it is beneficial it might overcome some of the limitations of the current DTW and classical feature extraction approach. For this new implementation there would be a need of a solid evaluation strategy to measure them, showing the importance of contributions on evaluation.

4.3.3 Final thoughts

We can garner some final thoughts as we conclude this examination of audio-to-score matching and its evaluation strategy expansion. This task is by no means a straightforward endeavor. The complexity of music, encompassing a vast array of genres, tempos, tonalities, and instrumental combinations, dictates the intricacy of the problem at hand. Harmonic nuances, as showcased through our experiments with chromagrams, are paramount in classical contexts but may be less pertinent in more contemporary or electronic domains.

Evaluating such a task also carries its problems and difficulties. For meaningful results, one needs lots of experimenting and parameter tuning that takes a lot of time and effort; it is by no means a menial task.

Our study's reliance on DTW and harmonic features sets the stage for further exploration. The promising horizons of neural networks in related fields also signal potential applicability here. Neural architectures can potentially learn nuanced features and alignments directly from the data, bypassing the constraints of traditional methods. Yet, a cautious approach is warranted. The complexity and computational demands of neural models and their notorious "black-box" nature can be a double-edged sword.

In essence, the world of audio-to-score matching remains full of challenges and opportunities, and the task of evaluation will be crucial in its advancement. As technology and computational techniques advance, so will our understanding and capability to

navigate this intriguing confluence of music and machine.

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Bibliography

- [1] Muñoz-Montoro, A. J., Cortina, R., García-Galán, S., Combarro, E. F. & Ranilla, J. A score identification parallel system based on audio-to-score alignment. *Journal of Supercomputing* **76**, 8830–8844 (2020).
- [2] Clausen, M. F. K. M. Audio matching via chroma-based statistical features.
- [3] Hu, N., Dannenberg, R. B. & Tzanetakis, G. Polyphonic audio matching and alignment for music retrieval. URL <http://www.onicos.com/>.
- [4] Raffel, C. & Ellis, D. P. W. Large-scale content-based matching of midi and audio files. URL <http://www.fluidsynth.org>.
- [5] Raffel, C. & Ellis, D. P. W. Optimizing dtw-based audio-to-midi alignment and matching.
- [6] Morsi, A. & Serra, X. Bottlenecks and solutions for audio to score alignment research. URL <https://www.music-ir.org/mirex/wiki/2021:>.
- [7] Raffel, C. Learning-based methods for comparing sequences, with applications to audio-to-midi alignment and matching (2016).
- [8] Ens, J. & Pasquier, P. Building the metamidi dataset: Linking symbolic and audio musical data. URL <https://github.com/craffel/midi-dataset>.
- [9] Du, X., Yu, Z., Zhu, B., Chen, X. & Ma, Z. Bytecover: Cover song identification via multi-loss training (2020). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2010.14022>.

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- [10] Yesiler, F., Serrà, J. & Gómez, E. Accurate and scalable version identification using musically-motivated embeddings (2019). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1910.12551>.
- [11] Yesiler, F., Serrà, J. & Gómez, E. Less is more: Faster and better music version identification with embedding distillation (2020). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2010.03284>.
- [12] Kosugi, N., Nishihara, Y., Sakata, T., Yamarnuro, M. & Kushirna, K. A practical query-by-humming system for a large music database (2000).
- [13] Music information retrieval using query-by-humming based on the dynamic time warping (2015).
- [14] Carabias-Orti, J. J., Rodriguez-Serrano, F. J., Vera-Candeas, P., Ruiz-Reyes, N. & Nadas-Quesada, F. J. C. An audio to score alignment framework using spectral factorization and dynamic time warping.
- [15] Salvador, S. & Chan, P. Fastdtw: Toward accurate dynamic time warping in linear time and space.
- [16] Li, Z. *et al.* Speed up similarity search of time series under dynamic time warping. *IEEE Access* **7**, 163644–163653 (2019).
- [17] Silva, D. F., Giusti, R., Keogh, E. & Batista, G. E. Speeding up similarity search under dynamic time warping by pruning unpromising alignments. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* **32**, 988–1016 (2018).
- [18] Tang, J., Liu, G. & Guo, J. Improved algorithms of music information retrieval based on audio fingerprint. 367–371 (2009).
- [19] Tralie, C. J. Early mfcc and hpcp fusion for robust cover song identification (2017). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1707.04680>.
- [20] Agrawal, R. Towards context-aware neural performance-score synchronisation (2022). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2206.00454>.

- [21] Dixon, S. Live tracking of musical performances using on-line time warping.
- [22] Nakamura, T., Nakamura, E. & Sagayama, S. Real-time audio-to-score alignment of music performances containing errors and arbitrary repeats and skips. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio Speech and Language Processing* **24**, 329–339 (2016).
- [23] Dorfer, M., Arzt, A. & Widmer, G. Learning audio - sheet music correspondences for score identification and offline alignment (2017). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1707.09887>.
- [24] Dorfer, M., jr., J. H., Arzt, A., Frostel, H. & Widmer, G. Learning audio-sheet music correspondences for cross-modal retrieval and piece identification. *Transactions of the International Society for Music Information Retrieval* **1**, 22 (2018).
- [25] Tanprasert, T., Jenrungrot, T., Mueller, M. & Tsai, T. J. Midi-sheet music alignment using bootleg score synthesis (2020). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2004.10345>.
- [26] Agrawal, R. & Dixon, S. A hybrid approach to audio-to-score alignment (2020). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2007.14333>.
- [27] Simonetta, F., Ntalampiras, S. & Avanzini, F. Audio-to-score alignment using deep automatic music transcription. 1–6 (IEEE, 2021).
- [28] Wang, W., Pan, J., Yi, H., Song, Z. & Li, M. Audio-based piano performance evaluation for beginners with convolutional neural network and attention mechanism. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio Speech and Language Processing* **29**, 1119–1133 (2021).
- [29] Thickstun, J., Harchaoui, Z. & Kakade, S. Learning features of music from scratch (2016). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1611.09827>.
- [30] Bertin-Mahieux, T., Ellis, D. P. W., Whitman, B. & Lamere, P. The million song dataset. URL <http://www.infochimps.com/>.

- [31] Mcfee, B. *et al.* librosa: Audio and music signal analysis in python (2015).
URL <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mh0dbtPhbLU>.

Appendix A

Appendix

The code that has been used for this thesis and the google drive folder with content examples of the audio mentioned in the results analysis can be found in these links:

- Code: [Link to Github](#)
- Audio examples: [Link to Google Drive](#)